

1. DATA FOR HIGH NUMERICAL APERTURE IMAGING

Table 1. Details of the acquisition parameters which correspond to the high NA objective lenses

Date acquired dataset	20201026	20220316	20200820	Units
NA	1.3	1.4	1.57	#
Objective vendor	Olympus	Zeiss	Zeiss	#
Part number	UPLSAPO60XS2	420782-9900-799	420792-9771-000	#
Magnification objective	60	63	100	×
Working distance	0.3	0.19	0.12	mm
Zeiss Optvar (M*1.6) used	yes	yes	no	#
Total Magnification with Optovar	88	100.8	100	×
Ham Orca Flash v3 pixel size	6.5	6.5	6.5	μm
Image pixel size	73.86	64.48	65	nm
Z-step distance/Z-pixel size	68	65	65	nm
Exposure time	80	100	150	ms

For this measurement, we use a 200 nm bead sample with yellow-green FluoSpheres™ Carboxylate-Modified Microspheres [ThermoFisher Scientific: F8811]. To prepare the sample, we firstly treated Carl Zeiss high performance (thickness 0.17 mm +/- 0.005 mm) with Poly-L-Lysine [Sigma Aldrich: P4707] for 15 minutes at room temperature. Then, we applied bead suspensions with different concentrations of beads in deionised water to the treated coverslips. The carboxylated beads interact with the Poly-L-Lysine surface treatment and stick to the coverslip mostly without detaching when the mounting medium (ProLong Gold) is applied. The coverslips are washed with deionised water to remove unbound beads afterwards. After airdrying, the coverslips were mounted on glass slides with ProLong Gold (refractive index 1.46) and sealed with nail polish.

For the NA 1.3 and 1.4 objectives, a Zeiss Optovar 1.6× magnification changer was used. For the NA=1.4 objective, this results in a total magnification of 100.8×. For the Olympus objective, we have to account for the difference in tube lens focal length for tube lenses of Olympus (180 mm) and Zeiss (165 mm) to which the objectives of the respective vendors are designed for the calculation of the total magnification. Therefore, the total magnification of the NA=1.3 objective is calculated by $1.6 \times 60 \times (165 \text{ mm}/180 \text{ mm})$, which equals 88×. The Zeiss Optovar 1.6x replaced the typical 1.0x Zeiss tube lens, however, it has the same focal length than the 1.0x Zeiss tube lens of 165 mm. Therefore, for all objectives described above, a tube lens focal length of 165 mm was used.

2. DATA FOR VALIDATING THE PSFs AT DIFFERENT SETTING OF THE CORRECTION COLLAR

The PSFs at different coverslip correction collar settings were recorded on an EVOS™ M5000 microscope imaging system with an air PLAN S-APO 40× objective lens of NA = 0.95 and working distance of 0.18 mm [EVOS™ Olympus: AMEP4754]. The emitter that has been used for this measurement is 0.1 μm TetraSpeck microspheres [Thermo Fischer: T7279] embedded in Dako mounting medium of refractive index 1.3744 in liquid state at room temperature equal to 18.3°, and humidity 48%. The exposure time throughout this measurement was set to 80 ms. The laser power is 5.3 mW. We use a coverslip of thickness 0.17 mm. The precision on the coverslip thickness is unknown. The sample is prepared following the protocol given in [1]. The goal is to obtain a sample with the least possible embedding depth, but this is not necessarily the case. We do not have knowledge of the exact embedding depth.

Table 2. Parameters for the acquisition and processing of the data acquired from NA = 0.95

Folder	t_{col}	t_g^*	z_{step}	N_{bead}	S_1	S_2	z_{ROI}
Z-Stack 13-08-2021 01.08.18	0.15	0.19	120	28	$64 \times 64 \times 22$	$512 \times 512 \times 44$	39
Z-Stack 13-08-2021 01.15.19	0.16	0.18	120	16	$64 \times 64 \times 44$	$512 \times 512 \times 88$	55
Z-Stack 13-08-2021 01.21.20	0.17	0.17	130	41	$64 \times 64 \times 50$	$512 \times 512 \times 100$	50
Z-Stack 13-08-2021 01.27.01	0.18	0.16	130	36	$64 \times 64 \times 22$	$512 \times 512 \times 94$	52
Z-Stack 13-08-2021 01.32.30	0.19	0.15	130	28	$64 \times 64 \times 47$	$512 \times 512 \times 94$	45

t_{col} : Correction collar setting in mm

t_g^* : Corresponding corrected values of the coverslip thickness t_g^* in design condition in mm

z_{step} : step size in the z-axis in nm

N_{bead} : The number of beads that are averaged to obtain the reconstructed Exp-PSF

S_1 : Size of reconstructed Exp-PSF in pixels

S_2 : Size at which the simulated PSFs are initially computed in pixels

z_{ROI} : z-position in the simulated PSFs with size S_2 and the centre position of the region of interest (ROI) in the simulated PSFs with size equal to S_1 in pixel. The ROI is defined as the grid at which the test simulated PSF fits the Exp-PSF best (highest value of NCC). The first xy slice of the data is at a z-position equal to 0. At a given t_g^* , the value of z_{ROI} is the same for all the different methods. The values of this parameter are determined using the PSF from the slice propagation (SP-FFT) method. This process is described below.

The lateral size of each of the Exp-PSF is reconstructed at 64×64 pixels. The data at $t_g^* = 0.17$ mm is zero-padded to 512×512 pixels grid to retrieve the phase aberration. The best estimate of the phase aberration of the data at $t_g^* = 0.17$ mm is found at the 100th iteration. The PSFs at different corresponding corrected values of t_g^* are simulated and the retrieved phase is added in the pupil plane. This addition of the retrieved phase induces an axial shift of the PSF. Theoretical aberrant PSFs computed using the slice propagation method and with a double of the axial size of the corresponding Exp-PSFs are simulated to estimate the shift in the PSF at different values of t_g^* . We let the Exp-PSF to scan over the theoretical aberrant PSFs along the axial axis and obtain the centre position of the theoretical aberrant PSFs z_{ROI} in z at which the NCC value between the simulation and the experimental is maximal. The region of the simulated PSFs centred at this position and with the same size as the Exp-PSF are extracted from the simulated PSF data. Finally, we crop the simulated PSFs to have the same z-range equal to 44 slices and the results are stored in the PSFResults folder.

3. DECONVOLUTION

The raw data that has been used for this purpose was downloaded from [2, 3]. We deconvolve two different dataset, images of InSpeck green fluorescent bead of diameter $2.5\mu\text{m}$ [2] and *C. elegans* [3], using the PSFs calculated from the PSFToolbox that can be found in [4].

	Dataset	Spherical bead [2]	C. elegans [3]
Imaging parameters	Size in voxels	256 × 256 × 256	512 × 512 × 80 (cropped)
	Voxel size in nm ³	64.5 × 64.5 × 160	64.5 × 64.5 × 200
	Objective lens	Olympus Cell R with a 63×/1.4 oil objective lens	Olympus Cell R microscope with an UPlanSApo 100×/1.4 oil objective lens
	Emission wavelength in nm	530	DAPI ($\lambda_{em} = 477$ nm), FITC ($\lambda_{em} = 542$ nm), and CY3 ($\lambda_{em} = 654$ nm)
Constant parameters yielding to the aberration in the PSF	Sample refractive index	1.46	1.56
	Sample embedding thickness in μm	6.5	20
Deconvolution parameters	Minimization function	Limited-memory BFGS	
	Noise distribution	Poisson likelihood function	
	Regularization	None	Good's roughness of regularizer parameter equal to 5×10^{-5}
	Positivity constraint	Square	
	Number of iterations	75	
Slices displayed on the manuscript	XY slice at Z equal to:	100	64
	XZ slice at Y equal to:	123	151

Bibliography

[1]

https://www.mcgill.ca/lifesciencescomplex/files/lifesciencescomplex/bead_sample_preparation_for_psf_measurements.pdf re-accessed on 29.12.22

[2] <http://bigwww.epfl.ch/deconvolution/bead/>

[3] <http://bigwww.epfl.ch/deconvolution/bio/>

[4] <https://github.com/bionanoimaging/PSFToolbox-Matlab>